

LEXICAL AND SEMANTIC FEATURES OF INGOT WORDS IN MODERN ENGLISH

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ingot words, also called telescopic words, abbreviation, lexical and semantic feature.

ABSTRACT

In this article lexical and semantic features of word formation in English language are considered, in particular, classification of word formation are included in the theoretical part as well as samples of ingot words and structure. The material of the study was ingot words that included lexical and semantic features. Lexical and semantic features of ingot words in modern English are noted, word formation is described. The scientific and practical relevance of the work is determined by the importance of a comprehensive study of language assessment and evaluation tools. The undertaken analysis of the semantic plan of words-ingots allowed us to transmit emotional information or to enhance the expression of a statement and express some considerations that are important for linguistic semantics.

In the second half of the twentieth century, many European languages significantly expanded their vocabulary. Every year the dictionary of modern English increases by 15-20 thousand lexical units. These are striking changes that have taken place in just two decades.

The reasons for such changes in vocabulary in most cases are obvious: social and cultural changes within modern society, technological "revolution" and globalization. Whatever the reasons for language changes, researchers and language teachers have no choice but to study and take these changes into account in their work.

Among the irregular ways of forming morphological neologisms, the most productive in recent decades are

abbreviations that reflect the tendency to rationalize language, to save language effort. Despite the fact that abbreviations make up only a small percentage of the total number of neologisms, their number is growing. The same characteristics are marked by another word-formation process-abbreviation. Abbreviations are defined as "words made up of abbreviated initial elements (morphemes) of a phrase or formed by adding the initial letters of words or initial sounds". E.g. IT, ASAP, P, K, BTW, etc.

The components of the ingot word, truncated in the source words, concentrate the content expressed by the source word as a whole. In truncated elements such as para- (parachute),- tron (electron),- thon (marathon), cine- (cinema), tele-

(television), and others, there is a process of reinterpreting some part of the word.

The lexical units formed by a word combination and abbreviation meet these requirements the most. Collocation - the process of joining two (and sometimes more) words without taking into account their morphological structure and based mostly on the consonance or euphony of the connected parts.

Out of the vast mosaic of spheres of human activity, the most frequent use of bullion words is observed in the mass media and advertising. When we read a newspaper or magazine, there is a high probability that we will encounter a new word that is completely unfamiliar to us, the Creator of which may be the author of the article himself, who skillfully combines words that are already known to us. As a result, the new lexical unit looks quite unusual. For example, the word —alcoholic - is not new to us, but lexical units created on the same model, such as sleepaholic, foodaholic or shopaholic, are almost not found in the speech of people, although their meaning is quite clear to us and quite relevant in life. In modern society, there is hardly a woman who is not familiar with the diverse products of Maxfactor, cosmetics

advertising, which does not leave the screens of TVs and pages of various magazines. Before us is a word-ingot, the initial element of which max is the truncated first syllable of the word maximal-maximum, respectively:

- Maxfactor<maximal+factor -
(adjective +noun combination) -
maximum factor.

The max element-being part of the name of a respectable company, indicates the maximum improved quality of the product. In addition to media and advertising, bullion words have also found their

application in other areas of human activity. To medicine can be attributed to the merger:

eyeliser, - eyeliser<eye+ analyzer-eye analyzer.

The study of new vocabulary and ways of its formation cannot be overestimated, especially for those who study English as a foreign language. At the same time, the knowledge obtained on the basis of a foreign language is significant and important for deeper development of the native language.

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